

CAPRI Steel Simulation Framework

A real time simulation replica of the Sidenor's data architecture has been put into operation, using historical data as a starting point. This digital twin is running inside the CAP creating new data and storing it at corresponding databases depending on the type of data generated in the same way that it would work with real data.

The data created correspond to the different phases of the process but are correlated with each other (secondary metallurgy, casting, and hot rolling), so that each CSS can consume the necessary data to be able to function properly.

The entire simulator has been developed over the Low Code programming OSS (Open-Source Software) called Node-red, with allows us to create a digital twin of the Sidenor's entire process flow.

The simulator has been divided into 4 different stages that work together to create correlated data. The actual dataset which is being used as a base to run the simulator is made up of 2 sequences of 3 heats.

The development also includes the integration of the communication with CAP platform via Kafka Broker, to which it sends information regarding the 3 first stages (production data itself) and receives the feedback of the CSS5.

Stage 1 - Heat and Casting

The first stage of the simulator oversees creating secondary metallurgy heat composition data in sequences of 3 heats with 10 minutes of stop time between sequences. This rhythm is close to the real operation of the plant and creates up to 24 heats per day. The data is stored in a records table of a MySQL database (OSS).

Figure 1 - Heat and Casting simulation overview

Each heat then launches the casting measurement simulation, which creates a single datapoint per second per strand. The last value of each sensor is stored to a real time Redis (OSS)

database, and the historical timeseries data is stored in a InfluxDB timeseries database (OSS). During the simulation length sensor data is monitored to then be used by the second stage of the simulator.

Stage 2 - Billet Creation and Tracking

Using the casting timeseries data (cutting sensor and length), the system calculates when a new billet is created. These billets can be of different types depending on their number in the sequence, so the simulator determines their number, their actual length and assigns these values to them. Depending on this number, it also assigns the type of billet and then decides whether a tracking number should be assigned to it or not. Only "normal" type billets will have a tracking number since the rest are discarded to scrap and will not be processed downstream.

At the end of the day the simulator generates about 800 billets per day of which approximately 150 are scrap.

Figure 2 - Billet Creation and Tracking system

Finally in the last step of this stage of the simulator is to save this data as if the billet had been in the billet yard for 15 days and had already entered the rolling mill with its tracking code. The data is saved in a records table in a MySQL (OSS) database.

Figure 3 - Billet creation subflow detail

Stage 3 - Hot Rolling Mill

The third stage of the simulator is the billet processing at the hot rolling. This simulator creates 200 sensor data per second. It detects the peaks at the entrance pyrometer sensor and assigns the data of the period in which a billet is passing through the rolling mill to a specific tracking number (by adding +1 to the last processed tracking number).

Figure 4 - Hot Rolling Mill

The data is saved again in a real time Redis (OSS) database and in a InfluxDB (OSS) timeseries database.

Stage 4 – Quality

The same spike detection that is being used on the Hot Rolling mill data creation of the pyrometer it triggers the quality data creation. Using the tracking number of the hot rolling tracking system, the simulator retrieves the “of”, the “heatnumber” and the “billetid” from the database, then it makes a search to find the specific quality data file related to that “of” and “heatnumber” and assigns the data to the billeted.

At the next step based on the quality data the defected and rejected ratios are calculated to have the same KPI that is coming from the CSS5 risk estimation sensor:

- Defected ratio = defected kg / total kg
- Rejected ratio = rejected kg / total kg

With this calculated data added to the rar quality data, everything is packed up and stored in the MySQL database (OSS).

CAP integration Kafka

The data created on the different stages of the simulator is also sent to a Kafka broker to be processed by the CSS5 risk estimation sensor.

Figure 5 - Kafka Broker integration

Risk Estimation Feedback

The CSS5 processes the data per heat/sequence and writes back the risk estimation per each billet, so this feedback is collected and processed in a Node-Red flow and stored in a MySQL database to be plotted against the ratios calculated upon the quality stage of the simulator.

Figure 6 - Risk Estimation feedback

Simulator monitoring dashboards

In order to monitor the correct functioning and performance of the simulator, several dashboards have been created to visualize in a simple way the data saved in the different stages.

Figure 7 - Last heat composition monitoring dashboard

Figure 8 - Casting measurements monitoring dashboard

Figure 9 - Rolling mill pyrosensors monitoring

CSS5 predicted data vs real quality data

As has been explained on this document, the incoming data from the risk estimation sensor are the two ratios (defected, rejected), and can be compared against the real ratios based on the raw quality data. Doing a join between the quality database and the risk estimation database the ratios can be plotted in a way that correlations and deviations can be found.

Figure 10 - Risk estimation data against the real quality data ratios